

THE EFFECT OF LEARNING STRATEGY AND WRITING CONVENTIONS ON ENGLISH LANGUAGE COMPETENCY AMONG ENGLISH EDUCATION STUDENTS

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The Effect of Learning Strategy and Writing Conventions on English Language Competency among English Education Students

Rea Gabbey A. Lacerna,* Evelyn Erellana
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study aimed to determine the significant relationship between learning strategies and writing conventions towards the English language competency of English education students. This study engaged a quantitative design, utilizing a regression analysis approach. The participants of the study were the English education students from all year levels. There were 195 students who were randomly selected as the respondents for this study. Based on the results of the study, it was determined that the level of learning strategy is high and it was also determined that the level of writing conventions is also high. There is also a significant relationship between the learning strategy and English language competency; and writing conventions and English language competency. The results confirm the learning strategy and writing conventions influence the development of English language competency among the English education students. The study reaches the conclusion wherein the respondents of English education students are high in level of learning strategies and writing conventions. This means that the respondents manifested both learning strategies and writing conventions in enhancing their English language competence. It is recommended that the students should improve their skills more for them to be able to enhance their competency in English language.

Keywords: *learning strategy, writing conventions, english language competency, english education students, philippines*

Introduction

English language competency is the ability to use the English language successfully and appropriately in a variety of circumstances, such as speaking, listening, reading, and writing. It is significant as it provides students with the necessary skills for academic success, global communication, and future professional opportunities, while also encouraging personal and intellectual development. However, several studies conducted found that students were facing a lot of difficulties in English language such as lack of vocabulary, poor spelling, first language (L1) interference, and a poor understanding of grammatical structure (Farooq et al., 2020).

In Malaysian context, numerous employers assert that their graduates are unable to work since they cannot communicate in English. While most students passed the English exam, not all can effectively communicate in English. It is very evident that ESL students have limited opportunities to use English outside of the classroom, particularly in non-English languages. Not having English language competency can limit academic and career opportunities, restrict access to information, create communication barriers, and contribute to social and cultural isolation, ultimately impacting personal and professional development (Aziz & Kashinathan, 2021).

Moreover, in the Philippines, as English majors are expected to explain, discuss, converse, ask questions, or even respond and answer in English, they often stop talking or perhaps decide not to speak at all because they are struggling with what to say. The fact that second language (L2) learners try to use a language other than their own is one factor contributing to this challenge. They have a distinct experience than others who speak and think the same language (Acosta, 2022).

With these in mind, the researcher chose to carry out this study in order to assess students' English language competency in a concrete manner and to determine how learning strategies and writing conventions affect students' English competency. Additionally, this study was done to find out what kind of writing conventions worked best for the students or what strategies for learning they currently employ most frequently. This study was also carried out to ascertain whether and how these factors can assist pupils in overcoming obstacles and learning efficiently. Further, this study is pertinent to community improvement since it may provide useful and extra information that would offer fresh insights and understanding of English language competency and its impact on students and community members.

Moreover, there are other studies that is somehow related to this study such as the study of Yusuf et al. (2019) which was entitled "Cooperative Learning Strategies to Enhance Writing Skills among Second Language Learners" and Tran (2021), which is all about "The Use of Self-regulated Learning Strategies in Paragraph Writing at Van Lang University" emphasizes the use of cooperative and self-regulated learning strategies in developing or enhancing the writing skills of the learners. Another study by Golparvar and Khafi (2021) which was all about "The Role Of Second Language (L2) Writing Self-Efficacy In Integrated Writing Strategy Use And Performance" which focuses on the writing self- efficacy and writing strategy only in developing the English language competency. This study, however, determines the effect of learning strategies and writing conventions in enhancing the competence of students in English language.

The researcher had created a thorough dissemination plan that will help spread the study's significant findings. Through online platforms, publication sites, and other academic networking sites, the researcher hopes to share the study's findings with the Commission on Higher Education, English major students, English language researchers, parents, and English instructors. Additionally,

the researcher produced a video presentation that will be distributed and uploaded to Google Drive, where those who have given their consent can view the study's material and conversation. Additionally, the work was published by the researcher on a reliable publication website. This could facilitate the study's dissemination among all target groups.

Research Objectives

The study was conducted to look into the relationship of learning strategies and writing conventions towards the English language competency among English language students. Specifically, it was addressed to the following:

1. To determine the level of Learning Strategies in terms of:
 - 1.1. planning stage;
 - 1.2. doing stage; and
 - 1.3. reflection stage.
2. To determine the level of Writing Conventions in terms of:
 - 2.1. general english writing skills; and
 - 2.2. grammar, punctuation, and mechanics skills
3. To determine the level of English Language Competency in terms of:
 - 3.1. reading;
 - 3.2. writing;
 - 3.3. listening; and
 - 3.4. speaking.
4. To determine the significant relationship between;
 - 4.1. learning strategies and english language competency; and
 - 4.2. writing conventions and english language competency.
5. To determine which domain of Learning Strategies and Writing Conventions significantly influence the English Language Competency.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative regression- analysis research design. This design looked if learning strategies and writing conventions has significant relationship with the English language competency among the English education students. Quantitative research is the method of employing numerical values derived from observations to explain and describe the phenomena that the observations can reflect on them. This method employs both empirical statements, as descriptive statements about the meaning of the cases in real words not about the ought of the cases, and methods. It also applies the empirical evaluations intending to determine to which degree a norm or standard is fulfilled in a particular policy or program. Finally, the collected numerical data is analyzed using mathematical methods (Taherdoost, 2022).

In this study, quantitative research design is used, which is the best methodology to employ, as this study was only concerned with quantifying or testing whether the variables have a significant connection with each other. Furthermore, this study aims to define the connection of the variables with each other by collecting numerical data and to address specific questions.

In addition, descriptive correlation was used in this study. This refers to a type of study that investigates the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. It aims to identify if a correlation (or association) exists, but it does not establish a cause-and-effect relationship. In descriptive correlational research, the researcher measures the variables and examines whether changes in one variable are associated with changes in another. In this design, it is crucial to remember that correlation does not equate to causation (Siedlecki, 2020).

In this study, a quantitative research design and a descriptive-correlational analysis approach was used to examine the effect of writing conventions and learning strategies on the English language competency of English major students. Three main variables were included in this study: writing conventions and learning strategies as independent factors, and English language competency as the dependent variable. Students enrolled in English programs made up the study's respondents.

Meanwhile, regression analysis is used since it can be useful for predicting the outcomes and changes in dependent variables based on the relationships of dependent and independent variables. Regression enables in controlling the effect of one or more independent variables while investigating the relationship of one independent variable with the dependent variable (Ali & Younas, 2021).

In this study, regression analysis was used because it is well suited to this academic endeavor. Given that this study, sought to determine the relationship of learning strategies and writing conventions to the English language competency of the students in English education.

Respondents

The study involved Bachelor of Secondary Education students with a major in English enrolled in the Academic Year 2023-2024 at

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST). The respondents in the study were primarily drawn using Slovin's formula with a margin of error of 0.05. A total of 195 students out of 388 across all year levels on BSED English were the respondents of this study.

Moreover, to ensure an accurate distribution of samples, the researcher utilized stratified random sampling. This approach involves dividing the population into subgroups or strata. Stratified random sampling can help ensure that the sample is representative of the population and that each subgroup is adequately represented in the sample, which can increase the generalizability of the findings. However, this method requires that the population is well-defined and that the relevant characteristics for stratification are known (Etikan & Bala, 2017).

The stratified random sampling method is particularly appropriate in this study because the respondents will be chosen at random based on the strata, which in this case are the BSED English students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST). To compute for the sample, the researcher will gather first the data of the population of respondents through writing a formal request letter to the College Registrar, requesting access to the population of respondents. After getting the data, the statistician will give the following computed data indicating the sample appropriate for the study.

The study was conducted among students enrolled in the English teacher education program from all year levels. The institution has a total of 388 English education students, consisting of 191 first year students, 89 second year students, 80 third year students, and 28 fourth year students.

Consequently, the statistician will give the following computed data indicating the sample appropriate for the study.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondent

<i>Bsed English</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1st Year	191	96	25%
2nd Year	89	45	12%
3rd Year	80	40	10%
4th Year	28	14	4%
Total	388	195	51%

Instrument

The researcher employed modified survey instruments from online resources to quantify the elements. These modified surveys were employed in this investigation and underwent extensive expert evaluation before the research released questionnaires that are aimed at the students. The first set of questions assessed English major students' learning strategies with its indicators: planning stage, doing stage, and reflections stage was adopted from the study of Learning Strategies Questionnaires.

In addition, the second set of questions focused on the writing conventions of the English major students with its indicators: general English writing skills and grammar, punctuation, and mechanics skills as intended which was adopted from the study of ESLP 82 Questionnaire.

Moreover, the third set of questions focused on the student's English language competency with its indicators namely: reading, writing, listening, and speaking. These were modified and adapted into a reliable questionnaire. This was adapted from the study of Eslit and Michael (2023).

A rating system called the Likert scale is employed to gauge beliefs, dispositions, or actions. It starts with a query or statement and ends with five or seven answer statements. The choice that most closely matches the respondent's attitude toward the statement or question is selected. The best applications for Likert scales are in the measurement of unobservable individual traits or traits lacking a hard, precise measurement. These can be factors that influence conduct, such as attitudes, sentiments, or opinions (Bhandari & Nikolopoulou, 2020).

A Likert scale was used to measure the extent of agreement or disagreement concerning statements regarding the impact of communication strategy and communication style on the communication apprehension of the students. This scale allowed the research to gather data that is straightforward to analyze and comprehend, helping to assess participants' preparedness for self-directed learning, which is a crucial aspect of English education students. Participants were given instructions to indicate their answers by marking a number associated checkbox. They were asked to utilize a five-point Likert scale, which ranges from 'always' to 'rarely'. Following this, the scores for these responses were combined across the items to provide participants with an overall score.

Procedure

The following procedures were followed by the researcher when collecting the data, they needed for the investigation.

Crafting the Questionnaire. The researcher crafted the questionnaire with the journal articles and related internet research which can possibly related to the variables in this study.

Revision and Validation of Questionnaires. After the modification of questionnaires, it will be submitted to the panels of experts in

order to evaluate and contextualize the learning. The researcher will follow the advice of those panels as well as improving those revisions until it is approved for use.

Requesting Approval to Carry out the Study. Through a letter, the researcher requested permission to the College President of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology to conduct the study among Bachelor of Secondary Education, Major in English students of the aforementioned school. After getting consent from the institution's college president, the researcher will proceed to the Vice President for Academic Affairs, and College Registrar.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. After receiving permission from the college president to conduct the study, the researcher asked the class representatives and class mayors to distribute the questionnaires to the appropriate respondents of the study.

Collection and Tabulation of the Data. After performing the survey, the researcher took and analyze the collected data from the respondents. The statistical data was analyzed, and the results were interpreted.

Data Analysis

The data gathered through the questionnaires were tallied and treated using the following statistical tools. The following statistical tools were used in the computation of data and to test the hypothesis at alpha 0.05 level of significance.

Mean. This was used to determine the level of learning strategies, writing conventions and English language competency.

Pearson-r. This was utilized to determine the significant correlation between the quality of the communication apprehension, communication strategy, and communication style of the respondents.

Linear Regression. This was used to determine the relationship between learning strategies and English language competency; and writing conventions and English language competency, which are the variables of this study.

Ethical Considerations

The respondents of this study are college students from all programs at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology (KCAST). In this instance, the researcher made sure that the respondents' safety, rights, and reliance on the researcher as well as the study's goals would be treated with fairness and righteous action.

Furthermore, when conducting research with humans as respondents, researchers must adhere to the highest ethical standards. The primary goal of this quantitative investigation is to ensure that the study will be ethically sound in order to protect the human respondent's comfort. The researcher discussed how the study will be able to adhere to the following Denzin and Lincoln (2011) guidelines, which focused on the three key principles: informed consent, risk of harm, anonymity and confidentiality; and conflict of interest.

Renowned researchers Denzin and Lincoln highlight the significance of ethical considerations at all stages of research in their 2011 study. Their work focuses in particular on the intricacies of research inquiry, which frequently deals with delicate subjects, power relationships, and people's lived experiences. Their approach to ethics is deeply intertwined with the research process, recognizing the relational and contextual nature of working closely with human subjects. This work is part of their broader contribution to qualitative inquiry, where they and other scholars explore these issues in-depth.

In the context of this study, the research made sure that before giving their consent, participants are fully told about the nature of the study, its objectives, any possible risks or benefits, and their rights, including the right to withdraw. Also, the researcher made sure that the protection of participants' identities was anonymized and handled confidentially.

Informed Consent. It is the first crucial ethical principle to consider. The responders must be adequately informed about their obligations, the planned use of the data, and any potential penalties. Respondents must offer clear, active, and written consent to engage in the survey. They must also say that they understand their right to access their information and that they can alter their thoughts at any moment. An agreement between the researcher and the respondents may be considered during the process of acquiring informed consent (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In this case, the researcher added an informed consent question in the survey questionnaire, asking study participants if they agree to participate in the survey. When respondents are dubious about an agreement, they may decline. Informed decision-making and voluntary participation in the study are strongly encouraged. The researcher ensures that all responders to the study are passionate about it and eager to participate. It is vital that they base their responses on existing surveys while collecting data.

Risk of Harm, Anonymity and Confidentiality. The respondent's information must always be kept confidential or hidden, and promises have to go further than just keeping their names private to include refraining from using identity remarks and material. Anonymity and secrecy are important steps in safeguarding people from possible harm (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

The researcher made it clear to the respondents that their safety, identity, and personal information would be safeguarded, and that their involvement in the study was vital to them. This was according to the Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012 which protects the privacy of individuals while ensuring free flow of information to promote innovation and growth. In relation to this, the

researcher removes the identities from the data to ensure that it is error-free. A clean data collection contains no information that could be used to identify respondents, such as their names or residences. However, there is a possible risk of harm in terms of social liabilities when the data is carefully disclosed to others. As such, data of the study shall be maintained private and secured to avoid this incident from happening. Data shall be stored and destroyed three years after the study is completed.

Conflict of Interest. Conflicts are unavoidable and vary in significance but because they have a natural tendency to create preconceptions and biases about, or otherwise influence the thinking and behavior of investigators or researchers and authors, it is essential that the conflicts are managed appropriately and transparently. Present connections or prior actions of the researcher may result in a conflict of interest, which needs to be reported transparently in an ethical way (Horner & Minifie, 2011).

This viewpoint holds that the research activity's findings were unaffected by outside factors because the respondents were also students, and the researcher had no competing interests with the study. Conflict of interest only arises when the researcher has the power to use coercive methods to force respondents to participate, such as threats of termination of benefits, blackmail, or other forms of punishment (e.g. principals threatening to fire teachers or teachers threatening to fail their students if they do not respond to the survey.)

Results and Discussion

The responses of the respondents on learning strategy and writing conventions are presented and analyzed in this section. The topics discussed are level of learning strategy; level of writing conventions; level of English language competency; and correlations between learning strategies and writing conventions on English language competency of English education students.

Level of Learning Strategies on English Language Competency in terms of Planning Stage

The data presented in Table 2, revealed that the level of learning strategy in terms of planning had a total mean of 4.45 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that planning stage was always manifested by the students.

The highest mean score is 4.57 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This mean was obtained from the item no. 1 - Starting by setting goals for myself. This means that this item was always manifested by the respondents.

Moreover, the data also revealed the lowest mean score which is 4.28 with descriptive equivalent of high was obtained from item no. 5 - planning to do my best so that my teacher will praise me. This means that this item is oftentimes manifested by the students.

Table 2. *Level of Learning Strategies on English Language Competency in terms of Planning Stage*

<i>Planning Stage</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Starting by setting goals for myself.	4.57	Very High
2. Planning the steps that I need to complete.	4.46	Very High
3. Making sure that I am interested in what I will do.	4.54	Very High
4. Making sure that I will be good at doing it before I begin with the task.	4.42	Very High
5. Planning to do my best so that my teacher will praise me	4.28	High
Total	4.45	Very High

Level of Learning Strategies on English Language Competency in terms of Doing Stage

Presented in Table 3 are the mean scores of the respondents' responses regarding their level of learning strategies specifically in relation to the Doing Stage of the learning process. The data revealed that the level of the learning strategy of English education students in terms of doing stage had a total mean of 4.07 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that doing stage is oftentimes manifested by the students.

In addition, the highest mean score is 4.21 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This mean was obtained from the item no. 1 - keeping the steps in mind as I am working. This also means that this item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Moreover, the data also revealed that the lowest mean score which is 3.78 with descriptive equivalent of high was obtained from the item no. 5 - using the same strategies even if I have problems. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 3. *Level of Learning Strategies on English Language Competency in terms of Doing Stage*

<i>Planning Stage</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Keeping the steps in mind as I am working.	4.21	High
2. Turning the task into smaller, easier steps.	4.19	High
3. Giving all my attention to the task I am doing.	4.20	High
4. Keeping a record of how well I am doing.	3.96	High
5. Using the same strategies even if I have problems.	3.78	High
Total	4.07	Very High

Level of Learning Strategies on English Language Competency in terms of Reflection Stage

Presented in Table 4 are the mean scores of the respondents' response on their level of learning strategy in terms of reflection stage.

The data revealed that the level of the learning strategy of English education students in terms of reflection stage had a total mean of 4.08 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that reflection stage is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Moreover, the highest mean score is 4.21 with descriptive equivalent of high. This mean was obtained from the item no. 1 - checking my work to see if I have done it well once I am finished; item no. 2 - doing the tasks well because my teacher usually explains things clearly; and item no. 3 - doing the tasks well because of how much effort I put in. That means that these items are oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

The data also revealed that the lowest mean score which is 3.58 with a descriptive equivalent of high was obtained from the item no. 5 - giving up if I cannot do the task easily. This means that the students oftentimes manifested the said item.

Table 4. Level of Learning Strategies on English Language Competency in terms of Reflection Stage

<i>Planning Stage</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Checking my work to see if I have done it well once I am finished.	4.21	High
2.	Doing the tasks well because my teacher usually explains things clearly.	4.21	High
3.	Doing the tasks well because of how much effort I put in.	4.21	High
4.	Doing the tasks well because of how much effort I put in.	4.13	High
5.	Doing the tasks well because of how much effort I put in.	3.58	High
Total		4.08	High

Summary on the Level of Learning Strategies

Shown in Table 5 is the overall level of Learning Strategies of English education students in terms of planning stage, doing stage and reflection stage. The data revealed that the level of learning strategy has a total mean score of 4.20 with a descriptive equivalent of high. The high level could be attributed to high rating given by the respondents to majority of the indicators. This means that the respondents oftentimes manifested the items in planning stage, doing stage, and reflection stage. The cited overall mean score was the result obtained from the computed mean score 4.45 with descriptive equivalent of very high for planning stage, 4.07 with descriptive equivalent of high for doing stage, and 4.08 with descriptive equivalent of high for reflection stage.

Furthermore, the highest mean is the planning stage with the garnered mean of 4.45 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the level of learning strategy in terms of planning stage is always manifested.

On the other hand, the total mean for the indicator doing stage was 4.07 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that it is often manifested by the respondents.

Moreover, a mean rating of 4.08 for reflection stage as indicator of learning strategy obtained a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that this indicator was oftentimes manifested by the English education students.

Table 5. Level of Learning Strategies

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Planning Stage	4.45	Very High
Doing Stage	4.07	High
Reflection Stage	4.08	High
Total	4.20	High

Level of Writing conventions on English Language Competency in terms of General English Writing Skills

Presented in Table 6 are the mean scores of the respondents' response on their level of writing conventions in terms of general English writing skills. The data revealed that the level of writing conventions of English education students in terms of general English writing skills had a total mean of 4.17 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the level of writing conventions of the students in terms of general English writing skills is oftentimes manifested.

Table 6. Level of Writing conventions on English Language Competency in terms of General English Writing Skills

<i>General English Writing Skills</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Writing a good introduction for an English essay	4.25	High
2.	Using a logical arrangement of paragraphs to support and develop my thesis statement.	4.14	High
3.	Writing clear topic sentences that identify the topics and controlling ideas of paragraphs.	4.12	High
4.	Writing a good conclusion for an English essay.	4.22	High
5.	Using appropriate vocabulary and word forms to effectively communicate with the reader.	4.14	High
Total		4.17	High

The highest mean score is 4.25 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This mean was obtained from the item no. 1 - writing a good introduction for an English essay which means that this item was oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

The data also revealed the lowest mean score which is 4.12 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This mean score was obtained from the item no. 3 - writing clear topic sentences that identify the topics and controlling ideas of paragraphs. This means that this item was

oftentimes manifested by the students.

Level of Writing conventions on English Language Competency in terms of Grammar, Punctuation, and Mechanics Skills.

Presented in Table 7 are the mean scores of the respondents' response on their level of writing conventions in terms of Grammar, Punctuation, and Mechanics Skills. The data revealed that the level of writing conventions of English education students in terms of Grammar, Punctuation, and Mechanics Skills had a total mean of 4.15 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that this indicator is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

The highest mean score is 4.19 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This mean was obtained from the item no. 3 - using capital letters correctly when I write and item no. 4 - using the various present tenses correctly when I write. This means that these item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

The data also revealed the lowest mean score which is 4.09 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This mean was obtained from the item no. 5 - placing adjectives and adverbs in the right place when I write. This means that this item was oftentimes manifested by the students.

Table 7. *Level of Writing conventions on English Language Competency in terms of Grammar, Punctuation, and Mechanics Skills*

<i>Grammar, Punctuation, and Mechanics Skills</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Using grammar, punctuation, and mechanics well so my errors do not interfere with peoples' understanding of my ideas.	4.12	High
2.	Using correct word forms and parts of speech when I write.	4.17	High
3.	Using capital letters correctly when I write.	4.19	High
4.	Using the various present tenses correctly when I write. 4	4.19	High
5.	Placing adjectives and adverbs in the right place when I write.	4.09	High
Total		4.15	High

Summary on the Level of Writing Conventions

Shown in Table 8 is the overall level of writing conventions among the English education students in terms of general English writing skills and grammar, punctuation, and mechanics skills. The data revealed that the level of writing conventions has a total mean score of 4.16 with a descriptive equivalent of high. The high level could be attributed to the high rating given by the respondents towards the majority of indicators. This means that the respondents oftentimes manifested the items in general English writing skills and grammar, punctuation, and mechanics skills. The cited overall mean score was the result obtained from the computed mean score 4.17 with descriptive equivalent of high for General English Writing Skills; and 4.15 with descriptive equivalence of high for Grammar, Punctuation, and Mechanics Skills.

Moreover, the highest mean is the general English writing skills with a mean score of 4.17 and a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the level of writing conventions in terms of general English writing skills is oftentimes manifested.

The lowest mean score is the grammar, punctuation, and mechanics skills with a mean score of 4.15 and a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the writing conventions in terms of Grammar, Punctuation, and Mechanics Skills are oftentimes manifested by the students.

Table 8. *Level of Writing conventions*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
General English Writing Skills;	4.45	Very High
Grammar, Punctuation, and Mechanics Skills	4.15	High
Total	4.16	High

Level of English Language Competency in terms of Reading

The data presented in Table 9 revealed that the level of English language competency in terms of reading had a total mean of 4.20 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the level English language competency of the students in terms of reading are oftentimes manifested.

Table 9. *Level of English Language Competency in terms of Reading*

<i>Reading</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Scanning and skimming through texts in English effectively to locate specific information.	4.33	Very High
2.	Understanding most of the vocabulary in English texts.	4.17	High
3.	Comprehending technical terms and jargons in English texts easily.	4.22	High
4.	Reading and understanding academic texts in English	4.16	High
5.	Comprehending the main ideas and details of a passage in English materials I read.	4.10	High
Total		4.20	High

The highest mean was 4.33 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This was obtained from the item no.1 - scanning and skimming through texts in English effectively to locate specific information. This means that this item is always manifested.

Further, the data also revealed the lowest mean score of 4.10 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This mean was obtained from the item no.5-comprehending the main ideas and details of a passage in English materials I read. It means that this item was oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Level of English Language Competency in terms of Writing

Presented in Table 10 are the mean scores of the respondents' response on their level of English language competency in terms of writing. The data revealed that the level of English language competency of English education students in terms of writing had a total mean of 4.09 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the level English language competency of the students in terms of writing is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean score is 4.17 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This mean was obtained from the item no. 1 - writing grammatically correct sentences in English. This means that this item was oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

The data also revealed the lowest mean score which is 3.96 with descriptive equivalent of high. This mean was obtained from the item no. 4 - writing cohesive and coherent paragraphs in English. It means that this item was oftentimes manifested by the students.

Table 10. *Level of English Language Competency in terms of Writing*

<i>Writing</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Writing grammatically correct sentences in English.	4.17	High
2.	Writing creatively and expressively in English.	4.14	High
3.	Expressing my ideas and thoughts clearly in written English.	4.13	High
4.	Writing cohesive and coherent paragraphs in English.	3.96	High
5.	Using grammar and vocabulary in writing English sentences effectively.	4.06	High
Total		4.09	High

Level of English Language Competency in terms of Speaking

Presented in Table 11 are the mean scores of the respondents' response on their level of English language competency in terms of speaking. The data revealed that the level of English language competency of English education students in terms of speaking had a total mean of 3.97 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This implies that the level English language competency of the students in terms of speaking are oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean score is 4.03 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This mean was obtained from the item no. 3 - using appropriate grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation in English which means that this item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Moreover, the data also revealed the lowest mean score which is 3.86 with a descriptive equivalent of high was obtained from item no. 5 - using appropriate gestures and facial expressions when speaking English. This means that this item was oftentimes manifested by the students.

Table 11. *Level of English Language Competency in terms of Speaking*

<i>Speaking</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Speaking English fluently and confidently.	3.98	High
2.	Participating effectively in English discussions and conversations.	3.99	High
3.	Using appropriate grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation in English.	4.03	High
4.	Articulating my ideas and thoughts in spoken English clearly.	4.01	High
5.	Using appropriate gestures and facial expressions when speaking English.	3.86	High
Total		3.97	High

Level of English Language Competency in terms of Listening

Presented in Table 12 are the mean scores of the respondents' response on their level of English language competency in terms of listening. The data revealed that the level of English language competency of English education students in terms of listening had a total mean of 4.07 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the level of English language competency of the students in terms of listening are oftentimes manifested.

Table 12. *Level of English Language Competency in terms of Listening*

<i>Listening</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Following English conversations and lectures without difficulty.	4.04	High
2.	Extracting key information from English audio recordings.	4.18	High
3.	Listening for specific details and main ideas in English effectively.	4.09	High
4.	Listening and comprehending spoken English in a variety of accents and dialects.	4.01	High
5.	Understanding complex instructions and directions given in English.	4.01	High
Total		4.07	High

The highest mean score is 4.18 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This mean was obtained from the item no. 2 - extracting key information from English audio recordings. This means that this item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

The data also revealed the lowest mean score which is 4.01 with descriptive equivalent of high. This mean was obtained from the item no. 4 - listening and comprehending spoken English in a variety of accents and dialects; and item no. 5 - Understanding complex instructions and directions given in English. This means that these items are oftentimes manifested by the students.

Summary on the Level of English Language Competence

Shown in Table 13 is the overall level of English language competency among the English education students in terms of reading, writing, speaking, and listening. The data revealed that the level of English language competency has a total mean score of 4.08 and with a descriptive equivalent of high. The high level could be attributed to the high rating given by the respondents towards the majority of indicators. This means that the respondents oftentimes manifested the items in reading, writing, speaking, and listening. The cited overall mean score was the result obtained from the computed mean score 4.20 with descriptive equivalent of high for reading; 4.09 with descriptive equivalent of high for writing; 3.97 with descriptive equivalent of high for speaking; and 4.07 with descriptive equivalent of high for listening.

Moreover, the highest mean is the reading with a mean score of 4.20 and a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of English language competency in terms of reading was oftentimes manifested.

The lowest mean score is the speaking with a mean score of 3.97 and a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that this indicator was oftentimes manifested.

Table 13. *Level of English Language Competency*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Reading	4.20	High
Writing	4.09	High
Speaking	3.97	High
Listening	4.07	High
Total	4.08	High

Significant relationship between the Learning Strategies and English Language Competency

Shown in Table 14 was the result of the significant relationship between Learning strategies and English language competency of the English education students. Doing an in-depth analysis of the table, the total mean score of learning strategies was 4.20 with descriptive equivalent of high. On the other hand, the English language competency had a mean of 4.08 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that both of these variables are observed and manifested most of the time.

The corresponding r-value of the two variables are 0.592. The r-value helps in understanding the relationship between two continuous variables therefore, this indicates that there are 59% of the English education students who use learning strategies in developing their English language competence and 41% who do not. Furthermore, this indicates that there is a moderate correlation between the two variables which are the learning strategies and English language competency.

The corresponding p-value of .001 is less than the 0.05 level of significance which means that the relationship between learning strategies and English language competency is significant. The null hypothesis states that there should be no significant relationship between learning strategies and English language competency. Since there is a significant relationship between learning strategies and English language competency, this led to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Table 14. *Significant relationship between the Learning Strategies and English Language Competency*

<i>Variables Correlated</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision =0.05</i>
Learning Strategies	4.20			
English Language Competency	4.08	0.592	<.001	Rejected

Significant relationship between the Writing Conventions and English Language Competency

Shown in Table 15 was the result of the significant relationship between writing conventions and English language competency of the English education students. Conducting an in-depth analysis of the table, the total mean score of writing conventions was 4.16 with a descriptive equivalent of high and the mean score off English language competency which was 4.08 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that these two variables are manifested or observed most off the time.

The two variables have corresponding r-value of 0.760. Understanding the link between two continuous variables is aided by the r-value, which suggests that 76% of English education students employ writing conventions as a means of improving their English language proficiency and 24% who does not. Additionally, this suggests that the two variables—writing conventions and English language proficiency—have a moderate correlation.

Writing conventions and English language proficiency are significantly correlated, as indicated by the matching p-value of .001, which

is less than the 0.05 level of significance. According to the null hypothesis, writing conventions and English language proficiency should not be significantly correlated. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected since there is a strong correlation between writing conventions and English language competency.

Table 15. Significant relationship between the Writing Conventions and English Language Competency

Variables Correlated	Mean	r-value	p-value	Decision =0.05
Writing Conventions	4.16			
English Language Competency	4.08	0.760	<.001	Rejected

Regression Analysis on which domain of Learning Strategies Significantly influence the English Language Competency

Presented in Table 16 is the regression analysis on the influence of learning strategies on the English language competency of English education students. The data shows that the two domains of learning strategies namely planning stage and doing stage is a strong predictor of the English language competency among English education students.

The beta value of planning stage which was 0.261 indicates a positive relationship between learning strategies and English language competency. This suggests a moderate, positive effect of the independent variable- learning strategy on the outcome. As the predictor increases by one unit, the outcome variable increases by 0.261 units (or 26.1% of one unit in standardized beta). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

The doing stage has a beta value of 0.359 which also indicates a positive relationship between the predictor and the outcome, but the effect is slightly stronger than the 0.261 value. A beta value of 0.359 suggests a moderate, positive effect. A one-unit increase in the predictor is associated with a 0.359-unit increase in the dependent variable (or 35.9% in standardized terms). This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

On the other hand, one domain of learning strategies namely the reflection stage is considered weak and not good predictor of the English language competency since it obtained the beta value of 0.99. This suggests that the predictor variable has a near-perfect positive linear relationship with the dependent variable. This means that, after adjusting for different scales of the variables, the predictor has a very strong influence on the dependent variable. The p-value of this variable was 0.195 which is greater than 0.05, this means that there is no significant relationship between the learning strategy and the English language competency therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

The data analysis showed that doing stage appeared to be the strongest domain having the highest computed standard coefficient Beta 0.359. This means that for every unit increase in the deviation of doing stage, there is also a corresponding increase in the deviation of English language competency by 0.359. Therefore, doing stage have a strong impact on the English language competency of the students. it implies that affects the English language competency of the student to an extent since the use of strategies during the process of doing the tasks could aid in enhancing the English language competency of the students.

Table 16. Regression Analysis on which domain of Learning Strategies Significantly influence the English Language Competency

Independent Variable	Standardized Coefficient	t-stat	p-value	Decision
Planning Stage	0.261	3.917	<.001	H ₀ Rejected
Doing Stage	0.359	4.469	<.001	H ₀ Rejected
Reflection Stage	0.99	1.300	0.195	Do not reject H ₀

Dependent Variable: English Language Competency
 F-ratio: 36.713 Adjusted R square: .356

Regression Analysis on which domain of Writing Conventions Significantly influence the English Language Competency

Presented in Table 17 is the regression analysis on the influence of writing conventions on the English language competency of English education students. The data shows that the two domains of writing conventions namely General English Writing Skills and Grammar, Punctuation, and Mechanics Skills is a strong predictor of the English language competency among English education students.

The beta value of General English Writing Skills which was 0.461 indicates a positive relationship between learning strategies and English language competency. This suggests a moderate, positive effect of the independent variable- learning strategy on the outcome. As the predictor increases by one unit, the outcome variable increases by 0.461 units (or 46.1% of one unit in standardized beta). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

The doing stage has a beta value of 0.398 which also indicates a positive relationship between the predictor and the outcome, but the effect is slightly stronger than the 0.461 value. A beta value of 0.398 suggests a moderate, positive effect. A one-unit increase in the predictor is associated with a 0.398-unit increase in the dependent variable (or 39.8% in standardized terms). This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Table 17. Regression Analysis on which domain of Writing Conventions Significantly influence the English Language Competency

Independent Variable			Standardized Coefficient Beta	t-stat	p-value	Decision
	β	SE				
General English Writing Skills	0.423	0.052	0.461	8.076	<.001	H ₀ Rejected
Grammar, Punctuation, and Mechanics Skills	0.352	0.051	0.398	6.966	<.001	H ₀ Rejected

Dependent Variable: English Language Competency
F-ratio: 132.272 Adjusted R square: .575

The data analysis showed that general English writing skills appeared to be the strongest domain having the highest computed standard coefficient Beta 0.461. This means that for every unit increase in the deviation of doing stage, there is also a corresponding increase in the deviation of English language competency by 0.461. Therefore, doing stage have a strong impact on the English language competency of the students. It implies that affects the English language competency of the student to an extent since the use of writing conventions during the process of doing the tasks could aid in enhancing the English language competency of the students.

Conclusions

Drawing upon the results, conclusions were formulated in response to the questions posed in the preceding chapter. The respondents consistently reported a significant prevalence of learning strategies, indicating that this variable is observed most of the time by the students.

Based on the result of learning strategies as perceived by students, it was determined to be high. This means that the students most of the time observe the presence of the variable. Moreover, based on the result of writing conventions of the students, it can be also drawn that the level of writing conventions of the students was high. In addition, the students' English language competency was also determined as high. This means that the English language competency of the English education students was manifested most of the time.

Furthermore, the correlation between learning strategies and English language competency revealed a significant relationship between the two variables. The study shows that learning strategies has a high, positive, and significant relationship with the English language competency among English education students. This means that the first null hypothesis proposed in the study is rejected.

Moreover, the correlation between the writing conventions and English language competency also revealed a significant relationship between the two variables. The study also shows that writing conventions has a high, positive, and significant relationship with the English language competency among English education students. This means that the null hypothesis proposed in the study was rejected.

Based on the result of regression analysis, in learning strategy, all three domains have shown significant influence on English language competency. This means that the domains – planning stage, doing stage, and reflection stage – are significant predictors of English language competency among English education students. Accordingly, the model describes 35.06% of the statistical variation with an r-value = 0.592 and $p < .001$ in the English language competency of the respondents, while the remaining 64.94% refers to the other variables that have not been included in the study that may also affect the English language competency of the respondents.

Lastly, the regression analysis of writing conventions has two domains that significantly influence the English language competency of the respondents. This means that the domains – general English writing skills and grammar, punctuation, and mechanics skills – are significant predictors of English language competency. This also indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis proposed in the study. Accordingly, the model described 57.76% of the statistical variation with a r – value = 0.760 and $p < .001$ in the English language competency of the students, while the remaining 42.24% refers to the other variable that have not been included in the study that may also affect the English language competency of the respondents.

Based on the previously mentioned findings from the study, the following recommendations were formulated. Among the learning strategies indicators, it was found that doing stage had the lowest mean. Therefore, the following recommendations are given.

It is hereby recommended that the educational institution focus on emphasizing the use of learning strategies for the students. This includes teaching specific strategies such as summarization, note-taking, concept mapping, or mnemonic devices. Break them down into clear, manageable steps that students can follow. Through this, students will develop their own learning strategies in which they can use to improve their English language competency. Using learning strategies in developing English language competency offers numerous advantages that enhance both language acquisition and long-term mastery. Learning strategies refer to the conscious, deliberate actions learners take to improve their language skills.

Based on the results, Grammar, Punctuation, and Mechanics Skills had been identified as having the lowest mean among the writing conventions indicators. Consequently, a set of target recommendations was formulated to maintain this aspect.

Therefore, it is hereby recommended that education institutions should ensure that grammar, punctuation, and mechanics are taught across the curriculum, especially for English education students. Integrating grammar, punctuation, and mechanics skills into the

curriculum offers significant advantages for students' academic development and long-term communication abilities. These skills are fundamental to effective writing and comprehension and contribute to students' overall literacy and success in both academic and real-world contexts.

Moreover, the results also revealed that speaking had the lowest mean among English language competency indicators. This finding emphasizes the need for improvement in the communication and speaking of the students in English language. Therefore, the following recommendations are given.

It is hereby recommended that the educational institutions and instructors focus on adopting targeted strategies to improve students' speaking abilities. These strategies include establishing more environment where students are regularly exposed to spoken English both inside and outside the classroom. This can include English-only zones, student-led discussions, and extracurricular activities conducted in English. Being able to speak effectively in English offers numerous advantages for students in school, impacting their academic success, social development, and future opportunities.

Furthermore, in order to facilitate future research, it is suggested that a mixed-method approach be used when examining the complex interactions among learning strategies, writing conventions, and English language competency. While the current study used a quantitative research methodology with 388 students, there are several reasons why a mixed-method approach could be useful. When survey data is combined with qualitative information from focus groups or interviews, it can provide a more thorough representation of the perspectives of the students.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Rea Gabbey A. Lacerna

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology – Philippines

Evelyn Erellana, MAEd

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology – Philippines